

Modeling Radiation Heat Transfer of Natural Gas–Hydrogen Blends in a Lab-scale Oxyfuel Furnace

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Motivation

While, **oxy-fuel combustion increases thermal efficiency and reduces fuel consumption**. Replacing natural gas with hydrogen (H₂) is a primary strategy to eliminate direct CO₂ emissions in high-temperature processes, supporting the **decarbonization of “hard-to-abate” industries** such as steel production. Therefore, **fuel-flexible oxyfuel burners** capable of operating with pure hydrogen or hydrogen-enriched natural gas, depending on availability, are required.

Introduction

In the present work, Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) simulations of a lab-scale furnace equipped with a **staged oxyfuel NIPPON DiluJet® burner** are carried out at a thermal power of 320 kW and 40% staging, under various **natural gas–hydrogen fuel blends** to evaluate the impact of hydrogen enrichment on furnace performance. Moreover, since radiation is the main mechanism of heat transfer in high-temperature processes, **the impact of gas and soot radiation heat transfer modeling is examined**.

Courtesy of Nippon Gases Euro holding

Numerical model

Steady-state RANS

- Solver: Pressure-based Fluent 2023 R1
- Mesh: 760 k polyhedral cells
- Turbulence: $k-\omega$ SST
- Turbulent diffusion: $P_{rt} = 0.85$ and $S_{ct} = 0.7$
- Chemical kinetics: UC-SD R26S [Castellani (2023) JHE]
- Turbulence chemistry integration: EDC

Radiation modeling

- **Radiation heat transfer equation (RTE):** DOM
- Angular discretization: 5 x 5
- **Gas radiation:** FSKD – WSGGM (5-gray gases) [Losacker (2025) TSEP]
- 5 RTE: One RTE is solved for each gray gas
- 1 RTE: Single gray gas approximation w/ mean path length
- **Soot radiation:** $\alpha_{soot} = b_1 \rho_{gas} Y_{soot} [1 + b_T (T - 2000)]$ [Taylor & Foster (1980) CNF]
- Soot modeling: Moss–Brookes
- Two transport equations: soot mass fraction + nuclei

5-gray gas WSGGM calibrated using full-spectrum k-distributions

Results

Contour plots of temperature and normalized OH mass fraction

Offgas composition and heat balance

Temperature and heat flux along the furnace ceiling

Soot radiation interaction

Temperature and heat flux along the central cooling tube

Conclusions

- The staged oxyfuel NIPPON DiluJet® burner demonstrates high fuel flexibility with minimal impact on heat transfer and overall furnace performance.
- Radiation dominates heat transfer (over 96%) in the natural gas–hydrogen oxyfuel combustion. The WSGGM accurately predicts the flue gas radiative properties across the full range of natural gas–hydrogen mixtures.
- The single-gray gas approximation predicts temperatures and heat fluxes within ~1% of the full WSGG model (5 RTE) while reducing computational time by 70%, making it suitable for engineering-scale simulations.
- When considered, soot radiation becomes significant at high natural gas content, strongly affecting the temperature field and reducing radiative heat transfer to the cooling tubes.
- Accurate soot modeling in oxyfuel flames remains challenging due to uncertainties in soot mass fraction and absorptivity correlations, requiring further model development.